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Rheological evaluation of grape juice in stationary state: effect of gap choice and plate geometry, relationship with particle size, and shear flow modeling

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the plate model and the most appropriate gap for measuring the rheological properties of grape juice and to validate the dimensional correlation between the gap and the particle size of the fluid as proposed in the literature: the gap should be least ten times larger than the particle diameter. The juice was evaluated for its thixotropic effect, testing gaps ranging from 1.3 to 2.5 mm with a flat plate geometry. The best gap and plate type (smooth or rough) were determined by generating constant shear flow curves using a controlled stress rheometer. The third curve was considered to avoid thixotropic effects. The best gap was compared with the average particle size of the juice, measured by laser light diffraction. The data from the third curve with the best gap and plate type were fitted to empirical models for Newtonian fluids, Power Law, and Herschel-Bulkley models. The quality of the fits was

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assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the sum of the least squares errors (SSE). The choice of gap influenced thixotropy in the juice, with gaps of 1.75 mm and 2.3 mm resulting in a reduced thixotropic effect, possibly due to the breakdown of structures under higher shear stresses. Gaps of 1.3 mm led to compaction and serum expulsion due to particle size, while gaps of 2.3 and 2.5 mm exhibited non-typical dilatant behavior for juices. Gaps of 1.75 and 2.0 mm with a smooth plate and a 2.0 mm gap with a rough plate showed behavior typical of juices. The 1.75 mm gap was also 10.9x larger than the average particle size, meeting the recommended relationship. The Newtonian model was the best descriptor of the rheological behavior of grape juice, with an R^2 of 1 and the lowest SSE: 6.16×10^{-31} . Therefore, the 1.75 mm gap with a smooth geometry stood out as the appropriate condition for the rheological analysis of grape juice, besides requiring fewer samples and reducing costs in the process.

Key words: distance between plates, fruit juice, plate model, thixotropy.

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